

(DT), the coldest period during their tillering stage. The minimum temperature varied between 9.1°C and 14.5°C, and the mean temperature, between 14.8°C and 20.65°C. More than 90% of the aus entries had from negative to 0.59 RTR, but more than 90% of the boro were in the range of 0.10 to 1.59 (see figure). Negative to zero RTR indicated either failure to survive or no tiller production.

To compare tillering potentiality by group, the average RTR values of 50 aus and 50 boro varieties were determined at 10-day intervals up to 50 DT. During the 30-day period after transplanting, the boro varieties had 3 times higher RTR values, indicating their better adaptability to cold temperature. From 30 to 50 DT, the RTR values of the two groups were similar. The temperature during this period was higher than that of the 30-day period after transplanting.

Thus, the two traditional rice groups

may be considered as two ecotypes. Perhaps, during the evolution process, only the boro varieties of the

photoperiod-insensitive rice groups of Bangladesh became adapted to cold climates through natural selection. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Severe blast outbreak during 1979-80 boro in Bangladesh

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About a decade ago, blast was a major rice disease in Bangladesh. But with changes in cultivation patterns, the introduction of improved blast-resistant varieties, and changes from rainfed to irrigated culture disease incidence has remained low since 1968.

During the 1980 boro (Nov. 1979-May 1980), however, blast broke out in almost all regions of Bangladesh. Chandina, IR8, Pajam, and Pusa II were attacked (see table). Attacks on BR3, BR6, BR7, and Purbachi were, however, mild. BR8, BR9, and Pajam also had neck blast. No indigenous variety was infected. Severe infection destroyed fields of Pajam in Dacca and Sylhet areas; fields of Chandina, Pajam, and Pusa-II in Comilla; and fields of IR8 and Pajam

Incidence of blast during 1979-80 boro in some areas of Bangladesh.

Area	Blast difference ^a on different varieties						
	Chan-dina	IR8	Pajam II	Pusa II	Pur-bachi	Other improved varieties ^b	Local
Barisal	-	VS	L	-	M	L	N
Chittagong	L	VS	S	-	L	L	N
Comilla	VS	L	S	VS	L	L	N
Dacca	L	L	VS	-	L	L	N
Sylhet	L	L	S	-	L	L	N
Northern districts	L	L	L	-	L	L	L

^aVS = very severe (disease incidence [DI] 7-9), S = severe (DI 5-7), M = moderate (DI 3-5), L = low (DI 1-3), N = nil. A dash (-) means the variety is not grown in the area. ^bInclude BR3, BR6, BR7, BR8, and BR9.

in Barisal and Chittagong. At the Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra (DND) project area, IR8 was infected only in plots severely attacked by ufra nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*. In the north and northwest, only mild and scattered infections were observed but in east, south-east, and central Bangladesh the incidence was severe.

The following factors were considered favorable for the development of blast disease during that season:

1. From October 1979 to April 1980 there was low night (10-25°C) and high day (24-25°C) temperatures.

2. The relative humidity of the atmosphere was high (92-95% at 0600 and 44-77% at 1200) during this period.

3. Dew formation on leaves was quite heavy at night during those months.

4. The affected plots were mostly dry because of scanty irrigation water during early crop growth.

5. The affected fields were mostly at

slightly higher locations (medium high to medium low lands).

6. Farmers normally used low or even no potassic fertilizers during the last few years.

7. Rice is cultivated continuously in almost all three seasons in some places. Usually only Paiam, the susceptible var-

ety, is used for three consecutive seasons.

In addition to the above factors, the development of new virulent races of the highly variable causal fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* and the immigration to Bangladesh of spores of races different from those already present are also possible.

Thus, the identification of the new races and of the number of races existing in Bangladesh and efforts to find chemical control measures are immediate steps being taken in the research programs of the BRRI Pathology Division. Studies on the interaction of ufra and blast have also been undertaken. ■

Varietal and insecticidal trial against rice tungro virus

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A trial with 10 test cultivars, which aimed at determining the effect of insecticidal treatment on the control of the vector insect of rice tungro virus (RTV), was laid out in split plots with 3 replications during 1979 thaladi. The treatments were: root soaking with FMC 35001 24% EC at 0.04% along with 1% urea for 20 minutes, maximum protection in which carbofuran 3% G was applied at 0.5 kg a.i./ha 10, 25, and 45 days after transplanting (DT); and an untreated control.

ADT 32 and AD 7211 had low percentages of RTV while ADT 31 and AD 9105 had high percentages (see table).

Data on rice tungro virus (RTV) incidence from an insecticidal trial, Tamil Nadu, India, 1979 thaladi.

Variety	RTV incidence (%)			Mean
	Root soaking	Max protection	Control	
AD 10969	56.0	52.3	52.0	53.4
AD 7211	25.3	22.0	27.7	25.0
TKM 9	39.3	35.3	41.7	38.8
AD 6120	62.7	63.7	60.7	62.4
AD 12599	68.7	58.7	67.3	64.9
ADT 32	33.3	10.3	22.3	22.0
ASD 15	42.7	14.3	46.0	34.3
IR20	56.3	16.3	45.3	39.3
ADT 31	92.3	93.0	100.0	95.1
AD 9105	97.7	92.7	100.0	96.8
Mean	57.4	45.9	56.3	

C.D. (P = 0.05%)	Insecticidal treatment	Varieties	Interaction
	2.3	5.4	3.2

In seven varieties – ADT 31, AD 9105, AD 6120, AD 12599, AD 10969, TKM 9 and AD 7211 – insecticidal treatment did not appreciably reduce RTV incidence by controlling the vector

insects.

In IR20, ASD15, and ADT32, maximum protection gave good reduction of RTV. ■

Outbreak of glume discoloration in Haryana, India

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Grain spotting, also known as glume discoloration (GLD) or dirty panicle, appears sporadically each crop season in Haryana on Basmati 370 and late-emerging panicles of IR8 and Jaya. Seventy-two percent discolored grains was recorded on RP967-4-1-10 and 31.5% in Basmati 370 in the 1978 wet season. Of the mycoflora associated with harvested grains, *Trichoconis padwickii* (in 60-80% discolored grains) was predominant over *Curvularia lunata*, *Drechslera oryzae*, *Phoma* sp., *Fusarium*

semitectum, *F. moniliforme*, and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

A glume discoloration outbreak occurred in September 1979, after a long drought followed by rainfall and a storm when the crop was in the panicle-emergence stage. All emerging panicles

had dirty brown or black grains. Symptoms appeared before the milk stage, and caused farmers to fear that they would not even get seed for their next crop. Pollen grains were viable, but no one could predict if grains would form. High sterility of spikelets and their

Occurrence of glume discoloration (GLD) under natural conditions at the Kaul Rice Research Station, India, in 1979 kharif.

Score	GLD (%)	No.	Cultivars showing discoloration	
			%	Designation
1	<1	110	38	Improved Sona, PAU1-608A, Sabarmati, R36-2486
3	1-5	58	20	Pusa 2-21, Prasad
5	5-25	35	12	Palman 579, Sona, Badshah Pasand
7	25-50	37	13	Basmati 370, IR36, PR106
9	>50	60	20	Ratna, Jaya, RP967-4-7-4, RP967-4-1-10, RP967-11-4-22